

THE ROLE OF RUSSIAN-MEDIATED INDIRECT TRANSLATION IN THE DISSEMINATION OF CHINESE LITERATURE TO CENTRAL ASIA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19333577>

Keywords: *Indirect translation, Russian pivot language, Chinese literature, Central Asia, cultural dissemination*

This paper explores the pivotal role of Russian as a pivot language in the indirect translation and cross-cultural dissemination of Chinese literature within Central Asia, a region historically connected to China via the Silk Road. While indirect translation (or pivot translation) has long been marginalized in translation studies (Davier et al. 2023), its practical significance is undeniable in multilingual contexts like Central Asia, where Russian remains a lingua franca due to historical and geopolitical factors.

Focusing on Chinese literary works translated into Central Asian languages (e.g., Uzbek, Kazakh) via Russian intermediaries, this study examines the dynamic mechanisms of meaning transfer across three linguistic and cultural layers: Chinese source texts, Russian pivot texts, and Central Asian target texts. It investigates how Russian-mediated indirect translation shapes the reception of Chinese literature by analyzing translation strategies, cultural filtering, and the negotiation of power dynamics in post-colonial and multilingual settings. Specifically, the research addresses two key questions: (1) How do Russian pivot texts function as "double bridges" in mediating cultural-specific elements (e.g., historical allusions, philosophical concepts) between Chinese and Central Asian cultures? (2) What challenges and ethical issues arise in indirect translation workflows, particularly regarding visibility, authorship, and the preservation of source text integrity?

Drawing on case studies of contemporary Chinese novels and short stories translated into Uzbek and Kazakh through Russian, this paper argues that indirect translation, despite its complexities, serves as a strategic tool for promoting cultural dialogue and knowledge exchange between China and Central Asia. It concludes by proposing a framework for optimizing indirect translation practices to enhance the accuracy and cultural relevance of Chinese literary dissemination in the region.